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**APPLICATION OF ALGORITHM, PRECISION AND PREDICTION IN
AYURVEDA PART-1: THE PRE-REQUISITE OF LITERATURE, LIFE-GOAL,
PHYSICIAN QUALITIES AND DISEASE MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract

Imbibing an Algorithmic methods for assessment of an Ayurvedic issues is a critical task considering the available data of Ayurveda towards machine learning and other AI tools. In correlation with conventional science, there are efforts already started and got some success too. However, developing Ayurvedic tools on Ayurveda concepts for Ayurvedic management is a need of hour for an original Ayurveda launching. This marathon struggle will start with identifying the aspects of precisions and predictions in Ayurveda. Until, it is not recognised, calculated, and systematically presented, the application of Algorithm on Ayurveda for 'as a whole' concept, will not be finished. This review will explain the pre-requisite of understanding the human life in harmonisation with Ayurveda's view about creation of universe, aim of Ayurveda, goal of medical system and ethics of a physician. The knowledge of human body, its wholesome adoptability for livelihood pleasure is important to know for clinical application of system. It will also be very interesting to know the pattern of documentation (*Grantha*) in Ayurveda for those who wish to take benefit from Ayurveda.

Key Words:

Precision, Prediction, Algorithm, Ayurveda, Disease Management.

INTRODUCTION:

Globally, there is huge technological expansion in every sector of science including medicine. The consumers too, wholeheartedly accepts it for their progress and pleasure. The common factors observed in the technological development is an accountability of scientific tools and their wide applications among the end users. The necessity for global acceptance of a tool needs rationality, proof and have a justification for advocating the medicine / procedure. For accountability of an Ayurveda ideology, mathematical calculations are needed for measuring any biological matter/ function, which seems to be very prime step, at list at this stage.

Ayurveda is a holistic science and believes in 'drug as a whole' for clinical management. The literature of Ayurveda is a combination of inputs from various *Rishis* (scientists) who were engaged in the medical practices. Obviously, they have propagated their own ideologies and wrote their script for the welfare of human beings. Despite of different way of thoughts for Ayurveda system, there is a generalization of many concepts like *Panchamahabhoota*, *Tridosha*, *Saptadhatu*, etc. Hence, while reading these texts, there are two patterns are seeming to be framed. The one which indicates to adopt the generalized management guidelines (*Samanya Chikitsa Sutra*) and start treatment, which will tend the generalized clinical benefits. The second pattern informs us, to enter into the precise decoration of diagnosis/drug selection/ therapy selection and get ready with calculated output (*Vishesh Chikitsa*). In current scenario, both these trends are observed to be applied by the Ayurveda physicians. The first *Samanya* management is adopted by most of physicians and adhere generally with *Vyadhivipareeta Chikitsa*. However, there is very less work accomplished with *Vishesh Chikitsa*. The competitive world is demanding, more accountability, time management, user friendly, handy, like specifications, which boosts clarity in selective treatments. The consumer too, is fed up with burden of many diseases/ medications for managing their health conditions. In such situation, planning of precise medicine by assessing various factors of Ayurveda is a point where the journey of accountability starts. The talk on precision medicine is started from 2006 in USA. However, its roots are deeply imbibed in Ayurveda since centuries. Obviously, current precision medicine is generally talk about genetics, coding, affinity, phytochemical, proteomics, etc. Ayurveda have different approach for precision medicine. With minimum doses, calculated time, adopting numerous parameters, the precision can be possible in Ayurveda through its own scale of assessment. The task is not so simple and need much clarification cum experimentations for end results. Hence, before entering the precision methods for algorithmic calculation, the pre-requisite in terms of understanding the Ayurveda science is to be accepted. This empathetic starts from knowing the development of Ayurveda, its intention, and its rational application for disease management.

Understanding life for disease management:

Ayurveda considers the formation of *Loka* (universe) is materialised through *Satva* (Immortal material), *Atma* (soul) and *Shareera* (physique). The *Purusha* (holistic human being), is the result of their conjugation by adding *Chetana* (sentimental). The same is the *Adhikarana* (topic of dialogue for disease management) in Ayurveda, where the medical system is going to be practiced and propagated for the sake of humanity¹. This entire reference highlights some accountable factors which cannot be expressed in the quantitative measurement at least at this stage. However, it believes some sort of Bio-Physiological energies which is responsible for creation of *Shrishti* (Universe). Ayurveda as a medical stream, starts its journey by exploring the human biology and simply adopting universal law of cosmos-formation and its physio-biological extract in human. More precisely talking about life, Ayurveda believes that Ayu (living system) is the conjunction of *Shareera* (physical body), *Indriya* (senses), *Mana* (mind) and *Atma* (soul) which is symbiotic or a connection between past life and the future life². It can be said that a biological matter (Physical body) with developed senses (*Indriya*) having some recognizable material (mind) forms the biological feature which make this conjugation a functional-item (Live Body). Surprising thing is, Ayurveda believes that this 'Live Body' is a connecting chain of Past life & Future life. According to Ayurveda, *Atma* (soul) is free from all ailments and is supreme. *Atma* is a cause of consciousness when it conjugates to the *Mana* (mind), *Indriyavastu* (objects of senses) and *Indriya* (sense organs) which is eternal and become the witness of all activities conducted³. Being a human centric, the formation of *Purusha* (Physical Body) with *Chetana* (sentimental) through *Satva* (Immortal material)-*Atma* (soul) - *Shareera* (physique), the entire theory of Ayurveda attains the category of an eternal. In this connection,

the concepts of 'happiness and un-happiness' and 'therapeutics and pathogens', their causes, signs, and dissemination are all becomes eternal. To simplify this eternity, Ayurveda took some basic justifiable issues to make them in an accountable framework. Accordingly, all the biological / physical matter are classified based on properties such as *Guru* (heaviness), *Laghu* (lightness), *Sheeta* (coldness), *Ushna* (heat), *Snigdha* (slimy), *Ruksha* (non-slimy), etc. The instant when the biological / physical matter (energy) which are outside the living body, encounter with living biological system, they tend to surge by equivalent properties and decline by opposite. Ultimately, the characteristic of these substances or and their phenomenon becomes everlasting and temporary. It is a like phenomenon of heat in the fire and the wateriness in water. Ultimately, Ayurveda's phenomena are supposed to performance as habitual intake of heavy things increases the heaviness and decreases the lightness in the body.⁴

Ayurveda is the source of knowledge related to life which communicates both the knowledge of *Sukha* (joy) and *Dukha* (suffering), *Hita* (benefit) and *Ahita* (harm), and explain their protocol of adoption or rejection. It provides the knowledge on any substance, its properties, and actions⁵. To calculate, what is the happy life? there are convincible criteria are mentioned. The individual whose *Shareera* (body) and *Mana* (mind) are disease-free, those who are gifted with *Youvan* (youth-ness), those who having good *Samarthya* (capability to execute any action), *Bala* (power), *Veerya* (Potency), *Yash* (Successfulness), *Paurusha* (courageous), *Parakrama* (dairing), *Gyana* (awareness), *Indiya Shakti* (perfect functioning of senses), *Aishwarya* (richness in getting all luxurious articles for any enjoyment), *Swatantrya* (freedom of roaming anywhere) are said to have a *Sukha* (happy life). The opposite of the same can be considered as *Dukh* Life (un-happy life)⁶. To achieve this happy life, the mentioned criteria is to be accomplished. Accordingly, those who are the well-wishers of all existences, who do not wish the capital of others, who are honest, peace loving, who are thoughtful before taking act, who are attentive, who balances the *Dharma* (ethics), *Artha* (finance) and *Kama* (pleasure), who respect intellectuals, who serve the aged, who have full control over *Anuraga* (lust), *Rosha* (anger), *Irshya* (envy), *Mada Vega* (addiction) and *Mana Vega* (mind), who constantly indulge in *Dana* (charity), *Tapasya* (working), *Gyana* (acquisition of knowledge) and favours the *Shanti* (peaceful life), who are involvement in *Adhyatma* (spiritual knowledge), who perform the work considering present as well as for the next life and who are with good memory and intelligence are said to be eligible for happy life⁷. All the sorrows of Physical and Psychological origin are caused by not knowing the knowledge of science of life or ignoring it. For an example, the Sun cannot help a visionless man to see things even with all its light, in a similar way Ayurveda generously guides for how to live a life which will attain the path of *Dharma*, *Artha*, *Kama* and *Moksha*⁸.

While describing the importance of an organ in the body, Ayurveda gives the importance to *Hridaya* (Heart/brain) for achieving the *Mahaphala* (purpose of life). The *Shadanga* (six divisions of the body, i.e., four limbs, head, and trunk) and its internal programming, all sense organs, and their perceptions and the *Atma* (soul-a coordinating stimulus) are in the *Hridaya*. The '*Chintya* (factor which analyses these senses)' too resides in *Hridaya*⁹. Hence, understanding the disease cannot be fulfilled without understanding Immortal composition of *Hridaya*. Further, by considering the *Sthana* (site) of *Atma*, *Chintya*, etc. in *Hridaya*, the protection of it becomes much essential. It is advocated to regularly adopt some measures to boost the functionality of *Hridaya*. In this regard, 1. Adhering to *Ahimsa* (Non-violence), for longevity of life, 2. *Veerya* (Potent food articles) for good strength. 3. Gaining more and more *Vidya* (Knowledge) for flourish in every field, 4. Attaining the *Jeetendriyata* (Self-control) for decorating the happiness, 5. Practicing the *Tatvabodha* (realization) for the feeling of any happening nearby, and lastly adopting 6. The *Bramhacharya* (celibacy) are the boosting factors of *Hridaya*¹⁰. Ayurveda also explain the calculation of lifespan based on such physiological parameters like functionality of *Indriya* (sensory), physique, Psyche, and an Intellectual performance. Based on pathological parameters like metabolism and symptoms of diseases, the life longevity is also calculated¹¹.

The medical literature and its view for disease management:

All the literature available related to Ayurveda are called as *Tantra* and forms the current Ayurveda Science. However, to understand the *Tantra* (*Tantrartha*) there are ten types of divisions which needs to be studied. These are 1. Understanding *Shareera* (Anatomy-Physiology), 2. *Vritti* (do's-dont's/Dietetics), 3. *Hetu* (Etiology), 4. *Vyadhi* (Disease), 5. *Karma* (Treatment), 6. *Karya* (Health), 7. *Kala* (Time/period/

Chronology), 8. *Karta* (Physicians), 9. *Karana* (Medicines) and 10. *Vidhi* (Therapies/ Procedures). This quote clearly directs that the scientific treatment cannot be fulfilled until these ten measures are fully addressed¹². The understanding of Anatomy-Physiology not in isolated condition but in concomitant with the body as a whole. The *Vritti* has a major role in nurturing body (mental/physical), if the *Vritti* is not-compatible to the nature of the body, certainly it will hamper the health. *Karma* i.e. prescribing various modalities including medicine is an important step for disease management which precisely to be selected. Accurate understanding the disease will simplify the prescription writing. Only subsiding the symptoms does not mean that the health is restored. The *Kala* refers to chronology (sequence) of any action in the form of time, season, doses, procedure, etc. The *Karta* i.e. physician who is a key of all these operations, must have sufficient capabilities to rationally apply the activities. *Karana* i.e. a tool by which the treatment can be done which will be an either drug or a technique. Lastly, the *Vidhi* i.e. Standard Operating Procedure which cover all earlier nine parameters. The real meaning from the coded Ayurveda literature can be known by identifying the place of content, its sequence, the author's intentions and the analysing methods (like *Tantrayukti*) of the same¹³. Ultimately, it cannot be taken as granted that the information suggested by one text will be suitable for the application in factor of another text. For example, compound formulations of Charaka Samhita are best suitable to the diagnostic suggested by Charaka Samhita only and may not be to the diagnostic parameters of Susruta Samhita as there is some ideological difference among both these literatures.

Ayurveda comments on the qualities of a perfect Ayurveda scholar. Accordingly, a scholar has a capacity to answer the questions regarding the classical text, its different sections, chapters, and exact topics, accurately. The scholar should be able to quote the lines of the manuscript, understand them and describe its characteristics too. The expectations can be completed by acquiring the meaning of the original text written by the Acharyas (scientist), replicate as-it-is in its complete form. It will enable to realise the depth of literature and have capacity to describe the it in elaborative as well as in concise way. While describing the knowledge, a supporting fiction with logical examples and applied narratives are to be done. Further, to explore the meaning of text, presumptions with rational application of the concepts are to be done in a conclusion form. Whatever the conclusions are drawn, it is understandable to the three types of scholars (above average, average and below-average). The activity is essential because the text is complicated to understand for proper meaning and its various aspects based on site of reference. The perfection in this activity can be attended by repeated conduction of this movement to clarity of concepts¹⁴. Charaka believes that out of four *Vedas* viz. *Rigveda*, *Yajurveda*, *Samaveda* and *Atharvaveda*, the physician should show his faithfulness to the *Atharva Veda* as it deals with the medical knowledge, where the disease management are explained through *Swastyayan* (auspicious recitation), *Dana* (Donation), *Bali* (sacrifices), *Mangala* (prayers), *Homa* (worship of fire), *Niyama* (moral discipline), *Prayaschita* (punishment of sins), *Upavasa* (fasts), *Mantra* (chants), etc. All these advocated for treatment as well as for living a healthy, long life¹⁵.

The Aim of disease management:

Having the good health is the benchmark for knowingly performance of ideal humanity (*Dharma*). The word *Dharma* has very massive and a wide of meanings. It advocates non-harming to any individual, non-irritating to self and not even to any object in the universe. In performance, it is differed in person to person and situation. In response to it, the law of nature always gives an optimistic value in the form of benefits of all. *Dharma* takes people at the top when followed correctly. The same is also applicable to achieve *Artha* (earning in a systematic and right way keeping the *Dharma* in mind). *Artha* reflects in gaining prestige, name, fame, sound relation in the society. The word *Kama* refers to all kind of pleasures, including sexuality, love, affection, marriage, arts, music, food, etc. *Kama* is an innate impulse to attain determinations. All should be completely tuned in a conscious stage for acquiring real pleasure. It can be achieved by good health only; the diseased condition is neither allow to do so nor can sense the feeling for the achievement. *Moksha* is a higher level of wisdom, permanent happiness, and self-realization. If anybody follows and achieve the previous three stages, the pathway for *Moksha* becomes easier¹⁶. The sequence of achievement should be like *Dharama-Artha-Kama* and lastly *Moksha*. Algorithmically, *Arogya* becomes the input and *Dharama-Artha-Kama-Moksha* becomes output¹⁷. Ayurveda accounts for quantitative measuring the type of life viz; good life (*Hita*), bad life (*Ahita*), blissful life (*Sukha*) and

sorrowful life (*Dukha*). It also advocates the guidelines and solutions to achieve the quality life¹⁸. To maintain a good health, the objective decided by Ayurveda is through gaining the *Dhatusamyā* (equilibrium of body constituents)¹⁹. An adoption of equipoise livelihood, not unfriendly to the orders of right path (*Dharma*), devoted to peaceful, one can attain happiness²⁰. The ultimate purpose of this science is to preserve the health of the healthy and cure the disease of the unhealthy²¹.

Characteristics of physician and his approach for disease management:

The quality physician is the one who take the individual towards the achieving the happiness, if he could able to precisely guide and treat. In Ayurveda, there is something beyond the sphere qualities of good physician other than attaining examinations and gaining operative skills. According to Charaka, the physician should be nurtured from well cultured family, has gone thoroughly in the literature, have practical knowledge of all medical procedures, have capabilities to perform the activities, have clarity in thoughts, have strong will power, have control over all the senses, have adequate knowledge about the physiological process of body and have ability to act as the situation demands. He should assess the biology of human body, its growth and development, also assess pathological states too. The profound knowledge of diseases categorically divided in curable, difficult-to-cure, managed-by-palliative care and incurable is must. The knowledge is needed for threefold essence of Ayurveda in the form of etiologic (*Hetu*), symptomatic (*Linga*) and treatments (*Aushadha*). He has an ability to clinically administer various medicines along with complete knowledge of foods, drinks, dietary rules, guidelines for lifestyle (daily & seasonal regimen), properties of substances, etc.²². A skilled physician is verified through knowledge of classical text with its deep meaning, documentation site of any information and knowledge of why it is placed to that site along with name of sub-section and purpose of explaining the same with all possible queries and the rational answers²³.

Discussion:

The issue of discussion on creating of Evidenced Based Ayurveda (EBA) is almost 2-3 decades ago and many experts have contributed as per their capacities. It is evidentiary that isolating a part of information and standardizing it, is not observed to be serving the original Ayurveda ideology. Hence, consideration of all aspects desired to fulfil the requisite management of disease can become the 'quantum' for precision. This quantum of requisites, is of many types starting from Type of Ayurveda Texts, Pattern of Education, Compound Theme of Ayurveda practice (all are explained above), basic concepts of *Dosha-Dhatu-Mala* (*Kriya*), *Vikriti* (pathology), *Swasthavritta* (Do's & Dont's), *Chikitsa Sutra*, etc. All these features can be united into a single pattern of sequence (a part of Algorithm) and executed with certain deadlines (called as 'output' a part of Algorithm). However, merging all the pattern in one sequence is not easy task as it has many variables. Though, the output will be broad and have little objective accountability, but represents core concept of Ayurveda. In the sequence, there will be short tasks with their little measurable parameters in entire process of management of disease based on *Chikitsa Sutra*. It is believed that every short task with its output can be standardized and projected as EBA. The purpose not only give rise to accountability of application of methodology but also represent the holistic Ayurveda. Further, these standardized short tasks with entire sequence as an evidence can become the basis of machine learning (AI tool / Ayurvedic tools). This marathon application will start with identifying the precisions in Ayurveda at every level of managing the disease (short tasks). This above review is a 1st part of precisions in the form of pre-requisite of understanding the actual human life, its harmonisation with Ayurveda, importance of 'creation of universe' for health, aim of Ayurveda, goal of Ayurveda medical system and ethics of a physician to execute it. The factors discussed herewith, will result into three major endpoints as; 1. what drug is selected (Quantum *Dravyaguna*), 2. for what it is selected (Reasoning: Quantum-*Nidana*) and 3. in which way it is applying (Sequence: Quantum *Yojana*). At this beginning stage, if these three endpoints are algorithmically calculated, probably an answer to the EBA can be justified without creating isolated partial parameters.

Conclusion:

Evidenced Based Ayurveda always does not mean to objectively demonstrate the output for the methodology planned for selected action. It may be or may not. But the methodology can be standardized in the form of Bunch / range / sequence / quantum. For its execution very short goals based on aim to execute the action can be planned and explained in the form of sequence will become an Algorithm to answer the evidences.

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